

Employment tracer study of Education graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

Tracer study is a way to give information about the status and performance of the graduates. Therefore, this tool determines if the knowledge and skills of the alumni members match with their employability. This tracer study aimed to focus on the employability status of education graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor City, Cavite. A total of 57 Education graduates from the Academic Years 2016 to 2020 were chosen to take part in this study. Using a survey questionnaire, it also provided general information, educational attainment, and employability status of the graduates. Results showed that majority of the Education graduates are currently employed and are working in their respective fields. Revisiting curriculum offerings should be emphasized to the needs of industry partners and stakeholders of St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), particularly in the alumni members of this institution.

Keywords: Employment; Tracer study; Education graduates.

To cite this article:

Mosende, K. D., & Ramas, R. J. (2022). Employment tracer study of Education graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia. *SDCA Journal of Education*, 7, 24-32.

Introduction

Graduate employability reflects the significance and quality of courses offered by higher education institutions (Cerado et al., 2020). Schomburg (2016) said that graduate survey results are essential for the analysis of the relationship between tertiary education and work. With the conduct of tracer study, educational institutions discover information for curriculum development and on what exactly the labor market needs in terms of employability of graduates (Gines, 2014). Cuadra et al. (2019) said that tracer studies are effective in retooling strategies and skills that are needed for the job market.

According to Yorke (2006), employability describes the skills, perspectives, and personality attributes that improve a student's chances of landing a job and succeeding in their field of interest for the benefit of the person, the workforce, society, and the financial system as entirety. In 2016, having a paid job no longer requires having a senior position inside the company or organization. Graduating students are increasingly starting their own businesses, organizations, and volunteer opportunities because of employment. Graduates involved in freelance short-term and part-time contracts and those who work while taking higher education are also considered as employed (Schomburg, 2016). According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, the employment rate in the Philippines in October 2018 was estimated at 94.9 percent which was at 95 percent in the same month last year; 17.8 percent of which was under the underemployed category (Bersales, 2018, as cited by Palay & Garcia, 2021).

Several tracer studies were made to determine the employment of undergraduate students. Macatangay (2013) conducted a study on the Computer Science graduates from Lyceum of the Philippines University in Batangas City, wherein results showed that most respondents work along their respective fields while others unrelated to their completed courses. Kalaw (2019) noted that while having work experience and developing occupational skills are two of the most important factors for the job employment

of the graduates, it is seen that most respondents have also experienced barriers such as the lack of learning experience and acquiring outdated skills which may affect them in getting a job. Meanwhile, Cornillez et al. (2021), in their tracer study about the teacher education graduates, revealed that the employability status of teacher education graduates was highly positive and that they chose Education program because of their parents and their academic performance during their high school years. Hingada (2021) said that most graduates considered salaries as one of the key factors on choosing to stay on their current employment.

Against this background, the main purpose of this study is to conduct an in-depth study on the status of graduates in the Education program of St. Dominic College of Asia. This tracer study aimed to focus on the employability status of education graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor City, Cavite. The focus of the study is to trace how SDCA graduates acquired their first job. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of SDCA's education graduates from the Academic Years 2016 to 2020 in terms of gender and civil status?
2. What is the level of current employment status of the Education graduates from 2016 to 2020?
3. How long did it take for the Education alumni members to have their first job after graduating from SDCA?
4. What are the recommendations of the graduates to better improve SDCA and its program?

Literature Review

College Education in the Philippines

In an article written by Robles (2012), the fact that the system of higher learning in the Philippines is based on the American model represents the source of this issue. The majority of schools and universities are for-profit enterprises. A total of 2,247 higher education institutions (HEIs) come from the Philippines, and 88% of them are privately owned educational institutions, according to official statistics. 1.74 million (or 60%) of the 2.9 million college students nationwide are pursuing their education in private institutions. State colleges and universities seem to be overcrowded, underfunded, and overworked despite being fewer in number (Robles, 2012).

According to JC Tejano, the former spokesperson of the Student Council Alliance of the Philippines (SCAP), says that "*all schools want to do is earn money.*" According to SCAP, they take much less action to guarantee quality. According to predictions from the government's Council for Higher Education (CHED), a private school student will typically pay 110,000 pesos a year in tuition. Tejano calls for the suspension of tuition and other costs. His group intends to reduce the load on regular people. It also seeks to make certain that more children receive an excellent education.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) noted that a full four-year program at a private university will cost 440,000 pesos to complete. Private schools tend to be the best and most costly, but this is also true of the worst and least expensive schools. Higher education is costly compared to what the average Filipino household makes. Based on the Philippines' Family Income and Expenditure Survey in 2015, the average family's annual income is 267,000 pesos while their average annual expenditure is 215 thousand pesos.

Private schools tend to be the most prestigious and costly, but this is also true of the worst and least expensive schools. Higher education is expensive compared to what the average Filipino household makes. College students' financial concerns are not limited to tuition. Board, accommodation, transportation, and other costs are not included in the CHED statistics. These expenses are significant. Professors frequently hear about students dropping out because they are unable to afford the transportation costs to get to school. There are further instances of students who are unable to concentrate because they are physically weak from lack of nutrition. To make matters worse, HEIs produce inventive ways to raise their prices. They

charge fees for "laboratories," "energy," and "development," among other things. Former Anakbayan official Antonio Pascua Jr. claimed a specific institution was imposing a "restricted fee" on students without making clear to them what it was for.

Former CHED chairperson Patricia Licuanan urges all HEIs to seriously think about any annual increases in tuition and fees. She asserts that each HEI should make wise financial choices to reduce expenses for its most crucial stakeholders—its students. The unfortunate reality is that a lot of students eventually find they can no longer pay their tuition and leave the HEI they had been attending. They either completely give up on their studies or go to a less expensive HEI. Obviously, the new institutions have become worse, but they also have a tendency of raising tuition. Licuanan affirms and asserts that "*quality education has a price.*" She includes expenses such as those related to academic wages, laboratories, devices, and others. She stated that tuition increases are therefore "necessary," although she preferred for them to be "justified, reasonable, and transparent." A survey conducted by Jenny Santos in 2017 revealed that due to financial difficulties, just 23% of Filipino people had the opportunity to complete their college degrees (PNA, 2017; Maga-Ao et al., 2019). Therefore, private HEIs remarked that they must increase tuition fees or may collapse.

Philippine Employment Rate

As declared by the Philippine Statistics Authority, in January 2015, the employment rate was predicted to be 93.4 percent, compared to 92.5 percent in January 2014. The employment rates in four regions were lower than the national average: National Capital Region (NCR) (90.7%), CALABARZON (91.4%), Ilocos Region (91.5%), and Central Luzon (91.5%). The labor force participation rate (LFPR) was expected to be 63.8 percent in January 2015. In January 2014, a similar LFPR (63.8%) was predicted. Both working and unemployed people over the age of 15 make up the workforce (Bersales, 2015).

Wage and salary workers comprised 57.8% of all employed people in January 2015, with those employed in private firms continuing to make up the majority of this group. In January 2015, they represented 44.7% of all employed people, compared to 44.1% in January 2014. The self-employed, who made up 28.2 percent of all employed people in January 2015 and 28.5 percent in January 2014, were the second-largest category of workers. Unpaid family workers made up the third largest group of workers, making up 10.9 percent of all working people in January 2015 and 10.6 percent in January 2014 (Bersales, 2015).

Methodology

This tracer study utilized a descriptive research design having 57 education graduate-respondents from the Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education for the school years 2016 to 2020. Non-probability sampling of individuals was used in the study, particularly in convenience sampling. In a non-probability sample, subjects are typically chosen based on their accessibility or the researcher's purposeful evaluation.

The alumni tracer study questionnaire is the main instrument of the study. The questionnaire consists of the following parts: general information, educational attainment, and employment data. The survey questionnaire was distributed in October 2021.

The Alumni Office provided names, addresses, and phone numbers for the graduates in Education from Academic Years 2016 to 2020. Respondents were given the questionnaire by the researchers in person, over email, and via Facebook Messenger. The responses obtained from the survey questionnaire underwent encoding, tabulation, and analysis. Descriptive statistics was utilized to determine the data frequencies and percentages in all categories. Frequency was used in order to generate information on the demographic profiles of the respondents. On the other hand, percentage was used to determine the size of frequency with reference to the whole population.

Results and Discussion

The graphs below discuss the results from the data gathered through a survey questionnaire using the validated alumni tracer study of St. Dominic College of Asia. The study attempted to investigate on the duration when the graduates have been employed after graduating from St. Dominic College of Asia.

Figure 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. 35.09% percent of the respondents are females and 64.91% are males. This shows that more respondents are males than females.

Figure 1. Gender of respondents

Figure 2 shows the civil status of the respondents. The figure reveals that 76 percent of the respondents are single when they graduated, and about 19.30 percent are married. Only 5 percent are single parents (either widowed or separated). This indicates that most respondents are single among all the participants.

Figure 2. Civil status of the respondents

Figure 3 presents the present employment status of SDCA graduates. About 89.47% are regular employees; 7.02% are probationary; and 3.51% are in contractual status. It is revealed that most respondents are employed on a full-time basis.

Figure 3. Present employment status of SDCA graduates

Figure 4 presents the employability status of the respondents. The figure below shows that 91% of the graduates were presently employed and only 9% were in unemployment status. This shows that more respondents have been employed in their respective jobs than those who were unemployed.

Figure 4. Employability status of the respondents

Figure 5 presents the postgraduate studies and advance trainings of the respondents. The graph shows that 56% of the graduates were not enrolled in postgraduate studies or advance training; 9% enrolled in masteral, 17% have ongoing vocational training, 2% in doctorate studies, and 16% in other advanced trainings. This implies that most of the respondents have not taken or have yet to take postgraduate courses in the future.

Figure 5. Postgraduate studies and advance trainings of the respondents

Figure 6 shows the locale of work of the respondents. The graph reveals that 89% of the alumni are presently employed in the local areas and only 11% are working abroad. This shows that more respondents are working in the Philippines than those who work in foreign countries.

Figure 6. Locale of work of the respondents

Figure 7 presents the long stay in the respondents' first jobs. The graph reveals that 18% of the employed graduates were on their first job and just started about one to six months ago from the date of the conduct of the study; 35% were employed for seven months to one year period; and 35% were employed in one to two years period. On the other hand, the remaining 12% of the respondents were employed for two to three years. This indicates that most respondents have been working for seven months to two years.

Figure 7. Long stay in the respondents' first jobs

Figure 8 presents finding the first jobs of the respondents. The figure shows that 44% of the respondents found their present job as walk-in applicants. About 5% were informed by their friends and relatives before they got their present job. Around 23% of the alumni were absorbed by the present company and the remaining 21% applied through job fairs. The graph implies that most respondents have sought their jobs through going to places personally.

Figure 8. Finding the first jobs of the respondents

Figure 9 shows the length of the respondents' first jobs after graduating from St. Dominic College of Asia. The graph reveals that 66% of the respondents were able to land their first job in one to six months; 30% of the respondents were employed within seven months after graduation; and approximately 4% were employed within one to two years after graduation. This shows that respondents have landed their first jobs through a short period of time.

Figure 9. Length of the respondents' first jobs after graduating from St. Dominic College of Asia

After the data had been collected, interpreted and analyzed, the following conclusions have been drawn. On demographic profile, the bigger percentage of the respondents is composed of females, and mostly are single. In terms of additional training or studies, 56% of the respondents did not enroll yet in any certificate programs. The bigger percentage of the respondents has been employed from one to six months after their graduation and are presently employed.

In terms of employment category, while some respondents work in fields unrelated to their degrees, the majority of respondents are employed in their fields of expertise. The respondents also stated their recommendations to help better improve SDCA and its programs. The following recommendations from the graduates are as follows:

- a. Expose the students to their scope of studies like volunteering and immersion.
- b. Hire faculty members who have substantial experience and academic preparation in teaching to give students more relevant insights about their career.
- c. SDCA should help in seeking jobs for their graduates.
- d. The school should help and guide students in their practicum or on-the-job training (OJT) program.
- e. Incorporate new technologies and up-to-date subjects and programs.
- f. Let students experience the real world especially when performing duties.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The majority of the SDCA graduates from 2016 to 2020 are presently employed while the others are unemployed and have been running their own business pursuit. Among the graduate-respondents, the majority of the subjects under this study are working in their field of specializations, and only a few of the total percentage of the respondents are underemployed. Revisiting curriculum offerings should be emphasized to the needs of industry partners and stakeholders of St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), particularly in the alumni members of this institution.

The graduating students must be given work-related seminars which may specifically be applied in their field of specialization. They must also be given ample time to practice for employment interviews which could help in strengthening their skills even before they plan to seek a job.

The school must conduct a scheduled pre-employment seminar in which the participants will be those graduates who have been unemployed due to lack of work-related skills or those who have been unemployed due to a planned change of career. The school must also invite graduates who have been working in their field of specialization for a good number of years already to be resource speakers of a pre-employment seminar to be able to give inspiration and insights that may be beneficial for the unemployed, under-employed, and those who will seek employment in relevance to their field of specialization.

The school must also emphasize other competencies which can be considered as work-related skills to strengthen the employability of graduates and to provide them with sufficient learning that they may be acquired to be multi-functional employees which can make them highly employable. Finally, the school must invest in instructors who are far more experienced to provide sufficient insights to the students. Also, the facilities and training for each of the mentioned programs must be improved to strengthen the skills that the graduates would need to be marked as highly employable both locally and internationally.

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